

SPEECH COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article discusses how primary school pupils develop speech competence through a cognitive approach. According to the article, cognitive language training helps primary school pupils develop speech competence. This method teaches pupils how to actively build expressions in specific life situations. Speech competency relates to a person's skill and willingness to utilize language for communication purposes. It is substantiated that exercises are leading in the work on the text: analytical, associative, and research. It is proved that the cognitive approach is based on the provisions of cognitive psychology, which implies a reliance on the principle of consciousness in the process of speech competence formation in primary school students. This approach directs the educational process to communicative activities, ensuring the proper level of students' speech competence.*

Keywords: *Speech competence, Cognitive skills, Primary school students, Speech skills, Structural components of speech action.*

Introduction

Modern tendencies of language education imply strengthening of the practical orientation of the process of teaching the language, subordination of the work on the language theory to the interests of students' speech development. Considering this, the goal of the primary school language course is to teach students to use English fluently as a means of communication, spiritual enrichment, and formation of intellectual culture. This approach ensures the proper level of speech competence of students, which is one of the most important conditions for successful socialization. This can be achieved through the transformation of language learning technologies and the development of innovative techniques. Linguistic competence is demonstrated by a native speaker's capacity to do necessary speech processes, create cognitive mechanisms (Pentyluk, Goroshkina, & Nikitina, 2011).

Observations of Uzbek language lessons and conversations between students and teachers revealed that primary school pupils vary from modern Uzbek literary norms, both in oral and written speech. Students are insufficiently aware of the Communication requires a strong culture of speech, as individuals typically use repetitive words and assume stylistic errors. On average, 6-7% of students demonstrated a high level of the language, while 35% had a sufficient level (Hreb, Hrona, 2020.)

The article aims to explore how primary school pupils develop speaking competence through a cognitive approach. To achieve this purpose, the following tasks were assigned:

- Identifying the content and structure of primary school children's speech competency.
- Describe the cognitive approach to structuring education in primary school.
- Demonstrate the cognitive methodology for teaching Ukrainian to primary school pupils.
- Evaluate the efficiency of the cognitive approach in teaching Ukrainian to primary school students.

Literature Review

Recent study indicates a growing interest among experts in establishing efficient language learning and development methods. This assertion is based on the active scientific search for solutions to the problem of communication. Demidchyk, G. conducted a study on the development

of communicative-speaking skills in primary school kids using auxiliary language elements, Lyashkevich, A. (formation of dialog speech of primary school students), Chuprin, O. (development of speech of primary school students with the use of multimedia means). Modern methodological science suggests teaching pupils in their native language to improve speaking abilities and enhance communicative competence (mastery of speech competence) occurs in the course of communication (active participation in speech activity).

The cognitive methodology is based on educational works by Ushinsky, K., Sukhomlinsky, V., Stelmakhovich, M., as well as linguistic research by Ermolenko, S., Kononenko, V., Kochergan, M., and Serazhim, K. Cognitive methodology's theoretical foundations are based on cognitive linguistics, which views language as a system in relation to the person who makes it possible to exist (Kochergan, 2003).

In cognitive linguistics, language functioning is considered a type of cognitive activity. Linguistic analysis investigates human consciousness, including its mechanisms and structures. Analyzing didactic works reveals that certain aspects of the problem are supported by scientific and methodological approaches. The theoretical and applied aspects of using cognitive technique for the development of speech competence in primary school kids are not well developed, so primary school instructors do not fully utilize this approach.

Methods

Cognitive theories of personality are founded on an individual's interpretation. The important objective is to determine the regulating role of psychological qualities that contribute to constructive learning. According to Chumak (2015), these traits can impact various aspects of the psyche, including perception, processing, and interpretation of educational material, as well as learning regulation that influences instructional techniques, student training, and independent work. An indicator of speech competence (and competence in general) is the Bloom taxonomy category. It defines the ability to implement the material studied in specific conditions and new situations. This includes the application of rules, methods, concepts, laws, principles, theories.

To assess communicative competence, we followed specific competence pedagogy rules, such as organizing students' experience, identifying successes and failures, and providing reference samples (Kasprzhak, A., Pometun, O., Khutorsky, A.).

Speech competence levels (cognitive, communicative-evaluative, and expressive) indicate the ability to follow instructions, follow patterns, perform integrated actions in training tasks, and serve as a role model for others in challenging situations.

Proficiency in the content and structure of speech

The term "speech competence" is often used in modern linguistic didactics. The scientific literature presents an uncertain understanding of this phrase. According to Pentyluk, M., speech competency refers to the ability to comprehend or create written or oral texts during speech activities. Bogush (2007) defines speech competency as the ability to use words appropriately in various settings, including facial expressions and gestures. Pentyluk, M. defines speech competence as "the ability to use knowledge in practice and use linguistic units" in the context of communicative competence.

There are various approaches to defining the substance of speech action. Zimnya describe speech abilities as the ability to realize the structural components of speech action, including orientation, planning, implementation, and control. We agree. In speech theory, orientation plays an important role. Researchers identify various aspects of speech action orientation: Message orientation involves objective language targeting, assessing the significance of the subject matter,

evaluating the effectiveness of the chosen linguistic means, and tailoring speech to the recipient's features and capabilities.

Speech skills acquire specific external manifestations depending on the characteristics of each particular type of speech activity. Depending on the orientation of the speech act to receive or deliver the speech message and the nature of the external expression, the types of speech activity are defined as receptive (listening, reading) and productive (speaking, writing). These two basic parameters divide 170 the types of speech activity into two large groups and determine the peculiarities of the speech skills depending on the type of speech activity (Vyshnik, 2012).

Receptive speech actions involve identifying a speech message's topic, dividing it into content, determining the key opinion and thoughts, organizing the message, and determining the entire content of the message (implementation), and the appropriateness of the message's perception.

Productive speech activities involve understanding the original concept of expression, integrating superphrasal content into a coherent message (orientation), predicting the basic thought of each content part, determining the structural and semantic unity of the whole text, establishing the message's logic (planning), verbalizing the predictive structure (implementation), and controlling the correctness of the creation.

Primary school students develop speech competence by listening, perceiving, and reproducing information, reading and understanding texts, participating in discussions, persuading and defending their points of view, and expressing their own opinions orally and in writing.

Organization of the educational process in primary school using a cognitive approach

Modern studies describe cognitiveness as a psychological activity that involves communication and thought. This is reflected in the developed cognitive skills. Cognitive talents are defined by researchers as an individual's ability to analyze, synthesize, and diagnose phenomena, as well as acquire knowledge independently and deal with diverse information during the learning process. Cognitive abilities refer to a capacity to work with knowledge independently during the learning process. Acquiring knowledge involves reproducing educational information, applying it to common problems in the subject area, and using it to solve new problems under new settings. Cognitive talents encompass organizational, operational, informational, and communication components. Clarifying the objective of text-making is crucial for demonstrating speaking competency. The first goal of the text-making activity is to teach primary school students how to organize their learning activities, search for information sources, create thematic dictionaries, divide texts into paragraphs, plan and annotate, and use the Internet. The operational component focuses on the ability to undertake cognitive, mental, and practical acts using algorithms, rules, and diagrams to construct texts.

The communicative component of cognitive skills refers to a set of talents that enable interactive conversation between people. Hrona (2017) defines this component as the knowledge and abilities required to apply new knowledge in numerous sectors, including drafting letters, invites, greetings, and online correspondence.

To organize the educational process at the initial stage, we can use a cognitive approach based on three principles: conscious learning (primary school students should learn to use language consciously in different situations), continuity (previously acquired language skills serve as a basis for practical skills), and sociocultural education.

Conclusion

Primary school students' speech competence is a key goal of the language courses, enabling them to communicate effectively, learn about the world, and complete important tasks. Implementing the cognitive approach improves language learning in elementary school, fosters multiculturalism, and enhances linguistic and conceptual understanding of the world. Learning the languages in primary school not only prepares students for further education, but also allows for free expression in various social and industrial settings. Teaching young pupils mostly focuses on developing and improving verbal communication skills. The cognitive approach, rooted on cognitive psychology, aims to develop linguistic competency in primary school kids through the principle of consciousness. The study of language in communicative activity is based on an objective category that reflects students' level of understanding.

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